

TEACHING ENGLISH TO DEAF STUDENTS ON THE INTERNET (ONLINE)

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ABSTRACT

This article promoted to deaf people especially hard hearing and deaf children. It is given general conception of teaching and learning English to children who are deaf. Moreover, effective methods and modern techniques is mentioned as way of teaching and learning English..

Introduction. Demanding for learning English is improving day by day all of the world. Because, if you can speak English you can speak with world. Also you will have chance to show your magnificent talent. So most philological researchers give their attention to improving consequences of teaching and learning English. They made lots of different methods, strategies and styles for English teachers and English learners.

Today's learners are very different: young, children, edult, man, woman, businessmen, doctor, teacher, builder and so on. They are also different from each other according to their age, gender, learning language ability, mental or physical skills.

There are many methods, research works for healthy people. They give their good results. But as healthy people, people with disabilities want to learn English. They should be have the same opportunity as healthy people to learning English. Nevertheless, there have lack of methods and styles to teaching and learning English to students who are disabilities. So in this article highlights the current problem's solutions in this field.

First of all, we must divide disabilities people according to their mental or physical ability[1]. They are:

- hard hearing or deaf
- Blind
- chronicle disease
- mental illness
- physical illness

Methods. What Parents should or shouldn't do?

If parents want to see their children 's success in English language, they should work hard with their children and teachers as the same time. They should pay attention to children's spiritual and physical conditions. For deaf children their parents only people who are counted on. So it is important for them their parents' opinion about their chances. they believe their parents every words and they try to gain praise from their parents.

Many parents would like to teach their children English at home, or they want to give help to their English but don't know how to start. It doesn't matter if you own English is not perfect[2]. The most important thing is that you are enthusiastic and that you give your children lots of encouragement and praise. Your child will pick up on your enthusiasm for the language. Don't worry if your child doesn't start speak English immediately[3]. They will need a certain amount of time to absorb the language . Be patient, and they will begin to speak English in their own time. Most parents think of their children cannot learn English because of being deaf. But it isn't wrong! First of all, parents must give motivation to their children. After that children begin to feel confidence in learning English.

There are given some important rules in order to teach children by their parents[4].

Establishing a routine

Using sign language alphabet

Playing games

- Using stories

Using everyday situations

Work with a teacher and a psychologist as a partnership

Establishing a routine

Establish a routine for you English time at home. It is better to have short, frequent sessions than longm infrequent ones. Fifteen minutes is enough for very young children. You can gradually make sessions longer as your child gets older and their concentration span increases. Keep the activities short and varied in order to hold your child's attention. Try to do certain activities at the same time every day. children feel more comfortable and confident when they know what to expect[5]. For example, you could play an English game every day after school, or doing exercise in the morning by showing finger spelling. If you have space at home you can create English corner where you keep any connected to English, for example books, games, DVDs or things that your children have made. Repetition is essential - children often need to practice words and phrases many times before they feel ready to produce them themselves.

Using sign language alphabet

Parents should more practise finger spelling letters together with their child. Because, sign language alphabet is the only thing to communicate for deaf children. When their teacher begin to learn this alphabet, Parents must learn and try to teach their child to this. If parents give help children to doing homework, children feel free themselves.

Playing games

Children learn naturally when they are having fun. Flashcards are a great way to teach and revise vocabulary and there are many different games which you can play with flashcards, such as Memory, Kim's game, Snap or happy families. Also watching videos of cartoons which are showed words and phrases using finger spelling by cartoon's heros.

Using everyday situations

The advantage of teaching English at home is that you can use everyday situations and real objects from around the house to practise the language naturally and in contex. For example:

- Talk about clothes when your child is getting dressed, or when you are sorting laundry (let's put on your red socks; it is Dad's T-shirt, etc.)

- Practise vocabulary for toys and furniture when you are helping your child to tidy their bedroom. (let's put your teddy bear on the bed!, where is the blue car?)

- Teach food vocabulary when you are cooking or going shopping. When you go to the supermarket, give your child a list of things to find (use pictures or words depending on their age.) Revise the vocabulary when you put the shopping away at home.

Using stories

Younger children love books with bright colours and attractive illustrations. look at the pictures together and say the words as you point to the pictures[6]. Later you can ask your child to point to different things, e. g. where's the cat? After a while encourage them to say the words by asking what's that? Listening to stories will get your child used to the sounds and rhythms of English.

Work with a teacher and a psychologist as a partnership

In order to gain the goal, parents, teachers and psychologists keep in touch very often. They should work together as a single team. They should aware of child's motions, spiritual conditions and physical conditions.

Results. Following by these methods hard hearing and deaf students could achieve more success in English. Also their parents have the opportunity to teaching their English by independently. If children are learnt by their parents, it would be greatful chance to occupy new language.

Discussion To sum up, as a healthy children have opportunity to study a foreign language, it should be chance to deaf children for it. If we support them, even it must be very small detailed, deaf children can achieve success in their studying.

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